

Cultural Variation in Children's Development of Executive Function

by

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Abstract

Executive Function skills (EFs) are cognition-related abilities that support children reach goal-directed behaviors and are essential for their growth in areas like learning (Obradovic et al., 2018). This study aimed to explore cultural variations in children's performance on EF tasks by focusing on standardized EF tasks vs. non-traditional EF tasks. Yucatec Maya (YM) children ($N = 10$) and middle-class U.S.A. children ($N = 11$) participated in the study. Data were collected using a variety of Executive Function tasks, and the sessions were video-recorded to facilitate analysis. We predicted that children from the US will perform better in traditional EF tasks, and YM children will perform better in culturally responsive EF tasks. Preliminary analysis of six participants' performance in two EF tasks, including The Tower of Hanoi and a non-traditional task requiring attention to two events simultaneously, revealed that most US participants successfully completed the Tower of Hanoi task with at least three discs. However, only two out of ten YM children could do the same, and eight chose not to attempt the task. Two YM children solved six disks correctly, staying on task and focused for over 35 minutes. On the other hand, no US children showed this level of performance and attention. YM children, on average, spent more time working on the Tower of Hanoi game ($M = 38$ minutes) than U.S. children ($M = 14$ minutes). In the dual-task EF test, which includes sorting bolts and nuts while paying attention to whether the water bucket gets full, YM children demonstrated sustained attention to the sorting task and paying attention to the water level and were less likely to go off task. In contrast, US children less often paid attention to both tasks and were more likely to go off task. The outcome of this study will further develop comprehension of how previous studies predominantly used traditional tasks to study EF skills of Maya children. Future studies should examine how Maya children perform better than U.S.A. children in culturally responsive tasks than traditional tasks.

Cultural Variation in Children's Development of Executive Function

Literature Review

Executive function pertains to the skillful handling of working memory, which facilitates the application of diverse aspects of higher-order cognition, such as problem-solving, planning, task flexibility, and reasoning (Gluck et al., 2019). Children are living in diverse and ever-changing cultural societies with their own beliefs, rules, and ways of learning and socializing. Do these differences in culture affect the early development of executive functions? Can some of an individual's thinking skills develop differently because of these cultural differences? Figuring out how an individual's surroundings affect their brain function while growing up might explain why some individuals' thinking skills develop differently than others.

Cultural psychologists have frequently posed inquiries regarding the definition of culture and its impact on cognitive processing (Wang, 2016). The significance of culture lies in its ability to offer discerning perspectives on commonly perceived universal psychological processes (Triandis, 1996). In conjunction with inherent biological tendencies, cultural norms, and values play a significant role in shaping an individual's cognition, interpretation, and reaction to diverse phenomena (Triandis, 1996). The environment that children are raised in allows them to pick the activities independently that are influenced by their culture, further creating culture-specific EF skills (Dobel & Lillard, 2023). In other words, culture influences how people think, talk about, and react to different things besides their innate tendencies. It creates rules about what things to notice and how important they are when looking at a small part of something.

Executive function is a pivotal aspect of human cognitive processes and accomplishments, effectively facilitating the exertion of control over one's thoughts and actions. This cognitive ability is particularly critical when engaged in activities that run counter to

prevailing habits, impulses, or inclinations (Doebel, 2020). The investigation of cultural disparities in children's development of executive function is a promising avenue for research due to its integral role in fostering proficiency in cultural activities, coupled with its susceptibility to the influence of culturally contingent daily encounters, which could have far-reaching impacts on children's development and educational attainment (Gaskins & Alcalá, 2023).

Executive functioning is a comprehensive phrase representing a collection of cognitive processes at a superior level that oversees and adjusts additional competencies and conduct. The functions encompassed in executive function involve the capacity to commence and cease goal-directed performance, to oversee and modify conduct when necessary, and to strategize forthcoming behavior in response to unprecedented demands and circumstances in children. Despite substantial research demonstrating the association between executive function and culture, only a handful of studies have examined the direction of the developmental pathways between executive function skills such as problem-solving, planning, task flexibility, and reasoning; therefore, little is known about how these constructs are influenced.

Aims

To further understand children's development of the executive function, this Honors project will use secondary data to find different results regarding cultural differences and how they will influence children's executive function. This project aims to understand how culture is vital in children's executive function because it helps us understand how people think and behave in different parts of the world. This can give individuals new ideas about how their minds work that we might not otherwise know. This project aims to accomplish three objectives. Firstly, it seeks to conduct a comprehensive analysis of existing literature to examine the impact of culture

on children's executive function, with a particular focus on those from Hispanic and American backgrounds. Additionally, it strives to identify the different sorts of executive function that differentiates among those children and how. Lastly, the project will culminate in an analysis of determining the advantages and benefits associated with using culturally significant research when studying children's development.

Introduction

Despite much research showing that EF and culture are connected, research less often includes Indigenous population. Therefore, this study focuses on EF skills with an Indigenous group - Yucatec Maya - in comparison to middle-class US children. Also, this study examines how children's daily activities influence their EF skills. The central theme explored in our ongoing work is the significant difference in children's performance based on traditional or non-traditional EF tasks. The information gathered before was recorded videos of a researcher who played different games with the children, like the Tower of Hanoi and sorting bolts and nuts. The purpose was to observe how the children reacted and solved each game. The Tower of Hanoi was analyzed first to investigate how EF and culture relate as a preparatory analysis. The Tower of Hanoi is a game that is very popular in the US and is seen just about in any doctor's office (refer to image one if unfamiliar with the game). Sorting bolts and nuts while paying attention to the water level of a bucket was used as a culturally responsive task for Yucatec Mayan children to see the difference in performance.

This project is essential and will contribute to future research because our objective will help others challenge beliefs about previously applied EF measurements to indigenous populations and broaden perspectives of indigenous children's EF skills. Comparably, other studies have found that the growth of cognitive flexibility and inhibitory control are two critical

mental abilities that can develop differently depending on what tasks children are asked to do and what culture they are from. Even if two cultures have similar ways of raising and educating children, these abilities may develop differently (Legare et al., 2018). Additionally, our study is analogous to the research of Gaskin & Alcalá (2023) to comprehend how the environment individuals grow up in affects their brain function, which can help provide insight into why children have different thinking abilities than others. Their research exemplifies how EF is essential to individuals' brainwork and helps them control their thoughts and actions. Studying the differences in how children from different cultures develop EF skills is a valuable area in developmental and cultural research. EF plays a crucial role in helping children become proficient at cultural activities, which can be influenced by the daily interactions specific to each culture; this could significantly impact children's development and academic performance. Furthermore, EFs are thinking abilities that help an individual get tasks done and are vital for children to learn and grow, especially when it comes to learning (Obradovic et al., 2018).

Hypotheses

The study examined how children's daily activities influence their development of EF skills, specifically focusing on an Indigenous group, Yucatec Mayan (YM), and middle-class US children using preliminary analysis. Performing preliminary analysis entails the researcher to grasp the difference between a population and a sample, recognize the significance of looking at the data visually, and should be able to provide a quantitative or qualitative summary of the data. In other words, preliminary analysis is to clarify the data, characterize the key characteristics of the data, and provide an overview of the findings (Blischke et al., 2011). Therefore, the hypothesis proposed is that there will be difference in performance between the traditional and

non-traditional task. It was hypothesized that US children would excel in traditional EF tasks, and YM children would perform better in culturally responsive task.

Methods

Participants

Twenty-four participants complete this study, but only twenty-one completed the tower of Hanoi, and six were analyzed for the bolts and water task. The participants were all children between the ages of five to seven, with an equal distribution of females and males. The population of the study were Yucatec Mayan (YM) and middle-class US children. The children involved in the study from Mexico had to have proficiency in Spanish, and US children had to have English as their primary language, be monolingual, white, and non-Hispanic. In the tower of Hanoi, there were ten YM children and eleven US children. For the bolts and water task there were three children from YM and three children from the US. The participants voluntarily participated in engaging in the Tower of Hanoi and the bolts and water task with their parents' consent. To conduct this study, parents were given consent they were aware of the purpose of the engaging in the activities and gave their child the option in engaging in the activities. At the end of the activities, children were given compensation for their time, which included a goodie bag with toys and candies. Parents were also eligible for \$40 in compensation for their travel and time. Parents were aware that they had the option to withdraw themselves and their child from this study at any time, and they would both still receive their compensation for participating.

Procedure

To conduct this study, children were invited to play games like Jenga, building blocks, memory games, and logic puzzles with a research assistant. In addition, parents were required to complete an online survey and respond to a series of recorded audio and video interview

questions. For research purposes, the child's activities were video recorded so that research assistance could better understand how the children were engaging with the activities. The data collection took place over a two-day session, each session being sixty minutes. As mentioned, there were many games involved, but this study only focused on the Tower of Hanoi activity and the bolts and water activity. Day one included water filling/bolt sorting, and day two included the Tower of Hanoi. YM and US children were invited to a room and played multiple games with the researcher. Dr. Lucia Alcalá has connections with a research assistant in Mexico, which enabled the YM participants to be directly from their country, and US children also participated from their country. The study setting differed for YM and US children. For instance, the YM children participated in this study in the research assistants' house in Mexico, and the US children were set up at the University of California Irvine's Learning Lab.

EF Task Analysis

The Tower of Hanoi task video excerpts ranged from three to fifty-five minutes, and the bolts and water dual task video excerpts ranged from sixteen to twenty-five minutes. For a visual of the Tower of Hanoi with participants in the study, refer to images two and three. To see a visual of the water and bolts task, refer to images four and five, which will include screenshots of the actual recordings used to analyze the games. Two research assistants analyzed the video recordings to establish reliability. The Tower of Hanoi noted how many disk moves were performed accurately and the time taken, whereas the bolts and water task had specific codes analyzed in ten-second increments. The codes for the bolts and water task included whether the child looks at water or bolts during the ten-second segment, the number of times the child looks at water, the child notices the water level and gets up from the table to shut the water off, initiates putting together a bolt pair, ongoing work in bolt pair, completes a bolt pair, child

initiates talk, self-talk, helps research assistant spontaneously (full or partial), change in behavior when research assistant leaves the room, whether child goes off task or child goes to the water station before container is full and time waiting in front of water if they do go before the container is full. To minimize possible biases, a detailed coding manual was created to specify the structure of the coding process (timings, counts, notes) and to define the codes. Each researcher was responsible for the initial analysis, comparing their codes and engaging in discussion to clarify discrepancies until a consensus was reached.

Results

In the Tower of Hanoi pilot test, U.S.A. children ($n = 11$) performed more disks accurately ($M = 2.73$, $SD = 1.85$), 95% CI [1.49, 3.97]. Mayan children ($n = 11$) performed fewer disks accurately ($M = 1.2$, $SD = 1.85$), 95% CI [-0.61, 3]. Reference table 1 for the summary of these results. Furthermore, U.S.A. children spent less time (14:06) attempting the traditional task than the Mayan children (14:49). An additional diagram is provided in the appendix to visualize the scores further.

In the bolts and water dual-task activity, Mayan children ($n = 10$) displayed sustained attentiveness to both tasks, spontaneous help to the adult researcher, and accurate estimations when the water reached the bucket's target line. Also, U.S.A. children ($n = 10$) demonstrated attentiveness to one task, helped the adult researcher when invited, and spent more time in front of the running water station. A diagram is provided in the appendix to visualize the qualitative differences between both groups.

Discussion

Executive functions skills are essential for children's goal-directed behaviors and learning (Obradovic et al., 2018). The purpose of this research study is to understand more about

how children from various cultures think and learn. The study was particularly interested in understanding how children acquire the ability to direct their attention and deal with problems on their own. The study focused on children in the US and Mexico to figure out the purposes mentioned. This study aimed to explore cultural variations in children's executive function skills using two types of EF measures: Standardized vs. Culturally relevant measures.

Results from the present study align as the U.S.A. children had better task performance than the Mayan children with the Tower of Hanoi activity. Similarly, young children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds in the US performed worse on EF tasks than with peers in more favorable circumstances (Obradovic et al., 2018). On the other hand, YM children performed better in the culturally relevant measure - water task - in which they showed EF skills as they paid more attention the water levels while continuing to sort the nuts/bolts (refer to image four). YM children also were able to demonstrate higher levels of inhibitory control and self-regulation as they were able to manage both activities even when the Research Assistant was not present. Findings from this study encourage those in developmental practice to invest in culturally sensitive measures to help spread culturally meaningful research, recognize the history of cultural bias, and catalyze change. Gaskin & Alcalá (2023) discovered implicit cultural assumptions after interpreting YM's unexpected reactions to traditional tasks; traditional EF experiments may not motivate certain populations. Studying cultural differences with EF skills and the influence of culturally contingent daily encounters may have far-reaching impacts on children's development and educational attainment.

Limitations

When considering all that was found in this study, a possible limitation in the current study was generalizability to a greater population because of the use of primarily Mexico and

only middle-class US children. The study did not look at children of other cultures or social classes, focusing only on middle-class children. Another limitation was that the study had a small, unequal sample size and missing participant data. The study was also a pilot study.

Future Directions

It is critically essential for further research to be conducted to discover new information related to this study. A future study could transition from open-ended, exploratory work to systemic, comparative studies. Another suggestion is a new study should incorporate additional sources of information like a parent or teacher ratings. This will help understand the child's daily duties and see whether this influences how the child acts when interacting with certain tasks like traditional and culturally responsive tasks. Lastly, it is also recommended that the cultural validity of current EF measures be examined to make them more culturally relevant (Jukes et al., 2024). This will enable a deeper understanding in order to make learning experiences more relevant and effective for ethnic minority students, using cultural knowledge, previous experience, frames of references, or performing styles.

References

- Blischke, W. R., Karim, M. R., & Murthy, D. N. P. (2011). *Preliminary data analysis*. SpringerLink. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-85729-647-4_8
- Doebel, S. (2020). Rethinking Executive Function and Its Development. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 15(4), 942–956. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691620904771>
- Doebel, S., & Lillard, A. S. (2023). How does play foster development? A new executive function perspective. *Developmental Review*, 67, 1–9. <https://doi-org.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/10.1016/j.dr.2022.101064>
- Gaskins, S., & Alcalá, L. (2023). Studying Executive Function in Culturally Meaningful Ways. *Journal of Cognition and Development*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15248372.2022.2160722>
- Gluck, M. A., Mercado, E., & Myers, C. E. (2019). *Learning and Memory* (4th ed.). Macmillan Higher Education. <https://bookshelf.vitalsource.com/books/9781319207335>
- Jukes, M. C. H., Ahmed, I., Baker, S., Draper, C. E., Howard, S. J., McCoy, D. C., Obradović, J., & Wolf, S. (2024). Principles for Adapting Assessments of Executive Function across Cultural Contexts. *Brain Sciences*, 14, Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci14040318>
- Kao, G., & Tienda, M. (1995). Optimism and Achievement: The Educational Performance of Immigrant Youth. *Social Science Quarterly*, 76(1), 1–19. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44072586>
- Legare, C. H., Dale, M. T., Kim, S. Y., & Deák, G. O. (2018). Cultural variation in cognitive flexibility reveals diversity in the development of executive functions. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-34756-2>

Obradović, J., Finch, J. E., Portilla, X. A., Rasheed, M. A., Tirado-Strayer, N., & Yousafzai, A.

K. (2018). Early executive functioning in a global context: Developmental continuity and family protective factors. *Developmental Science*, 22(5).

<https://doi.org/10.1111/desc.12795>

Triandis, H. C. (1996). The Psychological Measurement of Cultural Syndromes. *The American Psychologist*, 51(4), 407–415. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.51.4.407>

Wang, Q. (2016). Why should we all be cultural psychologists? lessons from the study of social cognition. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 11(5), 583–596.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691616645552>

Image one: Explanation of the Tower of Hanoi game

1. You can move only one disk at a time.

2. A larger disk may not be placed on top of the smaller disk. [gesture]

3. All disks, except the one being moved, must be on a peg, so you can't put them on the side. You cannot place the disks on the table while moving one of the disks.

Image 2: Female Participant from Yucatec Maya participating in the Tower of Hanoi task with Research Assistant.

Image 3: Male Participant from US participating in the Tower of Hanoi task.

Image 4: Bolts and water task. Yucatec Maya child engaging in water filling and bolts sorting activity.

Image 5: Bolts and water task. US child looking at the water station while research sorts bolts.

Table 1*Summary of Task Performance by Children Group*

Task	U.S.A. Children				Mayan Children			
	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	95% CI	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	95% CI
Disks	11	2.73	1.85	[1.49, 3.97]	10	1.2	2.53	[-0.61, 3]
Time	11	14:06	9:38	[7:37, 20:34]	10	14:49	15:47	[3:32, 26:07]

Note. *N* = 21. CI = confidence interval.

Diagram 1: Summary of the findings from bolts and water tasks

Water Filling/Bolts Sorting Dual-Task Activity

